

THE THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF GUIDE ACCOMPANIMENT AND TRANSLATION ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: This article is devoted to define several problems of tour guides from theoretical and empirical point of view and relevant solutions for them. It also gives information about tourism of Uzbekistan and challenges while interpreting.

Keywords: Uzbek tourism industry, tour guides, challenges, theoretical and practical concepts of tour guides.

The tourism industry of Uzbekistan is regarded as a crucial factor contributing the economic development of country. After gaining independence, Uzbekistan channel its attention to improving the tourism. Because tourism is one way of increasing financial and economic position of country. To achieve this, the tourism committee was founded. Then several occupations, such as manager, tour operator and tour guides are required. In this article, more observation will be given to the job called tour guide. Tourism industry in our country contains hospitality, hotels, recreational areas, historical spots, food, beverages and travel agencies. Translators and guides play important role to present them to the visitors. To be more precise, the tourist guide is the educated and professional person that shows a real and honest image of his/her country. Thus, tour guide is the first person that visitors or tourist groups meet and contact, so their responsibility is to provide security and all necessities tourists need. It is demanded that tour guide should be generous, polite, patient and outgoing in doing the job and able to solve problems easily. The guide leads the tourists to the attractive sites where he/she knows the history, importance and benefits of such places. There is always a necessity to improve the professional tourist guides through training and qualifications that help them in doing the job. All qualifications and skills of the tour guides should be associated on the connection with the visitors. To reach job satisfaction, organizations should provide the guide with high value and then benefit returns. Human resources is joint to impact on the productivity of tis issue. It emphasise on the increase of the knowledge, skills, qualifications of employees in all aspects. The importance of job satisfaction leads to the efficiency of employees. It evaluates the country's economic value and development. In our country tourism is a developing field which is making it known to the world. Especially, its ancient and historical areas, such as Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva worth taking into account. They are being more and more well-known among world tourists. Also such places play a principal role in domestic tourism, except outbound and inbound ones. As we know, Uzbekistan is rich in cultural heritage since ancient periods, the ages of The Great Silk Road. That signifies that guidance job has a long history, it has existed for ancient periods. There were people who guided the guests visited due to commercial or political reasons, along their country. In a short, tour guides have essential roles in tourism industry all the times. Precisely, the instrumental, interactional, social and communicative. The instrumental role includes: supplying direction, access, security and safety also organizing

and managing the groups; the interactional role includes: controlling relationships between local people and visitors experiencing different cultures; the social role includes: maintaining cohesion between tourists and providing humor, entertainment and several disciplines within them; the communicative ones includes: providing information, knowledge and translation about different places of their country. There are also managerial roles of tour guides as showed in the figure:

As a tour manager, they organize, control and manage the group; as a experience manager they responsible for managing relationships between locals and tourists facilitating memorable tours; as a destination manager, they determine places to show and control what the tourists see, do; as a time manager, they allocate time for visits and tours.

In spite of having an important influence on tourism industry, guides can be seen as a most affected people. They are often blamed for many reasons during their tour and also they are expected to handle all obstacles in tourism destinations. They usually work under great pressure, they are required to have communication, negotiation, personal skills and competences as well as provide information in a interesting and interpretive way; at the same time they should keep a good relationships between tourists and adjust to the rules, laws of the country. They also suffer from inconvenient job hours, low salary and information technology. Some of them may know little information about the destination or there is not enough support from government. And there is an explicit challenge, especially in our country, to maintain their family. Their job could result in breaking their family in order to not have a fixed salary to take home. Several challenges mentioned above was about empirical point of guidance. Regarding theoretical issues, they are also worthy for mentioning. Theoretical formulation of guides include their knowledge, particularly, occupational knowledge. The occupational knowledge is determined here as: the information, skills and all the experiences that the guide gained through their job. This includes understanding, learning, communication that emerged from the practical life space and socio-cultural life space. Tour guides may have

difficulty in gaining this knowledge according to their lack of theoretical information. To understand the occupational knowledge, the following figure comes to help:

The first category means that the tour guides observe the tourism performance of a destination. It gives them opportunity to analyse the tourism products and other performances of tourism operators. The second category includes the perceptions of tour guides on their industry roles. Being a guide requires to perform a broad range of roles. They manage the groups as a cultural operator, information provider, country representative and environment interpreters, in addition they perform their work as a tourism managers and operators. The third final concept illustrates the conceptions on their career. This one include their working conditions, motivations, career status and the socio-cultural aspects related to the guiding job. It supply information about how tour guides consider their status in the tourism industry and society. All knowledge above formulate theoretical aspects of guiding in tourism field. To be a professional guide, the whole practical and theoretical skills comes from such knowledge are needed. Nevertheless, in some cases, these skills are still in shortage for guides. To tackle this issue, several instructions should be taken into action. For instance, tour companies should apply some actions to release work stress and provide canteen rooms to have a rest for guides. They are requested to increase the level of safety and security in case there are disease and predicted accidents. The companies should continue the practice and training programs to enhance their competence and qualifications. There is also need for maintaining good relationships between guides and their colleagues to increase the spirit of team work. Moral incentives should be provided to improve payments in advance for the the seniority of recruitment. Companies should make efforts to rise monthly salaries and review them periodically to fit the cost of living and reach job satisfaction. To improve their theoretical skills, scientific meetings and projects should be organized. The opportunities are need to be created to train abroad in foreign agencies. To add, career-based subjects must be multiplied to gain more knowledge about field for the future tour guides. These recommodations are channeled to increase the knowledge about guidance field and as a result tourism industry in our country.

References:

Используемая литература:

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. The Worldview of Tour Guides: A Grounded Theory Study by Areej Shabib Aloudat – University of Bedfordshire, 249-257 p.
2. Journal of Association of Arab Universities for Tourism and Hospitality - vol.19 No.3, 2020, 113 – 130 p.
3. European Journal of Economics, Finance and administrative Sciences – 2011, ISSN 1450 – 2275, 34 -45 p.
4. Aviva, G & Arie, G satisfaction measurement in guided tours, Annals of Tourism Research – 1991, 177 – 185 p
5. American Journal of Industrial and Business Management, Scientific Research – 2011, 90 -93 p.
6. Airey and Shackley “ Tourism Development In Uzbekistan “. Tourism Management – vol.18,4, 1997, 199 – 208 p.